

Easter in the Time of COVID-19

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The feast of Easter celebrates the resurrection of Jesus from the dead. Jesus was willing to go to his passion and death despite being very afraid, only because he believed it was the will of his Father.

The courage and faith of Jesus at this time of trial is evident and we can draw lessons from it in the present situations in which we find ourselves and as our world struggles with the pandemic of COVID-19 caused by the Caronavirus.

Our Fear

A. Jesus' Fear: Often, fear arises because we are faced with what might seem like insurmountable and overwhelming odds. In the case of Jesus, the fear of death arose because as a Jew he would have believed that death meant total annihilation.

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The Synoptic Gospels are blunt when they narrate the fear of Jesus in Gethsemane before his arrest (Mk 14:34; Mt 26:37). The Gospel of Luke shows the fear of Jesus even more vividly (Lk 22:44). No community would have written about its Lord in such a manner if there was no historical core to these incidents. **However, Jesus does not let fear overwhelm him.** He does – and this is clearer in retrospect – the best thing he could do in the given situation: he prays (Mk 14:32; Mt 26:36).

B. Our Fear: The fear that many of us may feel in the present situation of COVID-19 is similar to that which Jesus felt. We too are faced with what seem at this moment like insuperable and undefeatable odds. We are struggling to contain and find a cure for infection due to the Corona virus, but it does not seem to be working as we would like.

Like Jesus, we must do what seems best under the circumstances namely, we must turn to God.

Our Dependence on God

A. Jesus' dependence on God: Even before he could begin praying, Jesus threw himself on the ground (Mk 14:35). At the time of Jesus, people prayed in one of two ways: standing (Lk 18:11,13) or kneeling (Mk 1:40; Acts 9:40). Prostration on the part of Jesus was unusual possibly because it was an unusual situation. This act of prostration communicated three things:

- a. It acknowledged the Almighty nature of God
- b. It acknowledged the nothingness of Jesus and
- c. It acknowledged that Jesus was available to do God's will.

Our dependence on God: Like Jesus we need to acknowledge that God is Almighty and all-powerful. We must acknowledge that even though there have been many and great advancements in science and technology, when it comes to finding a cure for a tiny virus we are incapable and powerless. It is only the higher power who can come to our aid. It is therefore time for reconciliation or a ceasefire of all our differences that we will work toward with one heart and one mind. Now is the time for unity even in our diversity.

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Our Prayer

A. Jesus' prayer: The prayer of Jesus in Gethsemane can be divided into three parts as follows:

- a. Addressing God
- b. An acknowledgement of the Almighty nature of God
- c. A petition (asking for what he wants)
- d. Ceding the initiative to God

3a. Jesus addressed God as "Father". This indicates intimacy on the one hand and trust on the other. He also acknowledges that he trusts that God (because God is father) will do what is best for him.

3b. Through the words "for you all things are possible" (Mk 14:36), Jesus acknowledges that nothing is outside the scope of God's power. Nothing is impossible for God (Lk 1:37)

3c. In his petition, Jesus asks **unashamedly** for what he wants namely: "remove this cup from me (Mk 14:36). The cup here refers to the cross.

3d. By the addition of the words, "yet, not what I want, but what you want." (Mk 14:36), Jesus shows that **DESPITE** his fear and despite what he thinks is best for him, he is willing to drink the cup **BECAUSE** it is the Father's will.

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B. Our prayer: Since God is bigger than any and all names or titles, it does not matter what name or title we use. What is important is to believe that God cares for us and our world and wants all of us to be saved and live in peace and harmony.

We must acknowledge that even though there have been many and great advancements in science and technology, when it comes to finding a cure for a tiny virus we are incapable and powerless.

What You Want

We must pray with confidence, faith and trust in God who **WILL** listen to our prayer. However, even as we do so, we must remember to add at the end of our prayer like Jesus did, “yet, not what I [we] want, but what you want.”

A. Jesus’ Perseverance in prayer and action:

It is noteworthy that at time in his life when he needed to hear God’s voice, there was apparently no response from God at all. Jesus interprets the silence of God to mean that he must do what God wills which here is the **opposite** of what he wanted. He gets up from his prayer fortified.

This fortification is seen in the scene that follows immediately after the prayer of Jesus, which is his Arrest (Mk 14:44-52). The final words of Jesus to his captors are “...But let the scriptures be fulfilled.” (Mk 14:47) which here mean “Let God’s will be done”.

B. Our perseverance in prayer and action: It is fairly easy to begin well, but not as easy to persevere. Though Jesus did not receive an answer from God or a response to his prayer, he did not let that fact stop him from persevering in prayer. We must follow suit. It is likely that to find a cure may take time. However, this must not stop us from continuing to petition God and asking for God’s help in our hour of need. Like Jesus we must persevere.

Our Cross

A. Jesus’ Arrest, Mocking, Scourging and Crucifixion: The Markan Jesus is portrayed as one whom everyone has abandoned. His **disciples desert him and flee** (Mk 14:50); the **whole Sanhedrin** condemned him as deserving death (Mk 14:63), in order to ‘satisfy the crowd’ Pilate had Jesus scourged and handed over to

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be crucified (Mk 15:15). Even as he hung on the cross he was taunted by the passers-by, the chief priests and those crucified with him (Mk15:30-32).

Not only does Jesus have no human support; at this hour he apparently receives no support even from God whom he addressed and knew as father as is evident in his cry, “Eloi, Eloi, lema sabachthani?” which means, “My God, my God, why have you forsaken me?” (Mk 15:34).

B. Our Crosses: At this moment there are many who will feel as abandoned as Jesus felt. There seems to be no support from any side. The psychological trauma will possibly be harder to bear than the physical.

The fallout of this pandemic will not only be on the ones who are infected but many others as well. The cry of all of us will be like the cry of Jesus.

The Vindication

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A. Jesus’ Vindication: Immediately at the death of Jesus there are two striking incidents which point to the vindication of Jesus. The first is that “the curtain of the temple was torn in two, from top to bottom.” (Mk 15:38). In all probability this means that now true worship is not in the Temple but on the Cross. That this is so is confirmed by the second incident in which the Centurion (a Gentile and so an unbeliever) acclaims Jesus in the words, “Truly this man was God’s Son!” (Mk 15:39)

B. Our Vindication: In the case of those of us who are ailing or will be infected, we will not be able to see the signs, but the

fact is that like Jesus we will be vindicated. In order for this to happen we must act like Jesus acted. This means that on our part we must do at every moment all that we have to do. We must not leave undone that which we have to do. We must take all the precautions that we have been advised to take and not test God. This is a time when strict discipline is required not only for one's own health's sake but also the sake of the health of others. It is possible that the foolishness or foolhardiness of some can cause great harm to many. This is why we need to be prudent and judicious. This does not mean however, that we must give in to fear. This can never be the response of one who has prayed. Fearlessness is called for, but fearlessness does not mean recklessness. This must be kept in mind.

Conclusion: The Absolute Vindication

Jesus' Absolute Vindication: More than the vindication on the natural level, it was the Resurrection of Jesus through which he was completely vindicated. In Mark this is portrayed through the Empty Tomb (Mk 16:1-8). The young man at the tomb confirms that Jesus is risen!!

Because of the resurrection of Jesus, we can say with confidence that death is not the end. There is the hope of a new and better life. We can also say that even when we carry a heavy cross and see no light at the end of the tunnel or the rainbow on the horizon like is happening at this moment, we need only the eyes of faith to see that God walks with us every step of the way.

The disciples of Jesus are to proclaim to the world that no one must give up or give in even when there is no concrete or tangible proof. Like Jesus they must keep on 'keeping on.'

In the light of our celebration of Easter even as we grapple with the pandemic of COVID-19, we will keep the hope that the God of the Resurrection visible in Jesus will continue to be our hope.